

Sensor Selection for High-dimensional Swarm Systems Based on Observability Analysis

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Abstract—The location selection of sensors in large-scale swarm systems is a prerequisite for further design of mechanisms to monitor the system states. This paper considers the required number and location of the sensors in a large-scale swarm system so that the observability of the overall system is satisfied. Firstly, by extending observability theory for swarm systems, some necessary and/or sufficient observability conditions related to the node-dynamics, network topology, coupling mode and measured outputs are obtained. Secondly, based on the above observability conditions, an algorithm for deciding how many and where to place the sensors is designed, which can be implemented in a polynomial complexity time. Finally, an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) swarm system is employed to verify the effectiveness of the theoretical results.

Index Terms—swarm, observability, sensor selection, networked system

I. INTRODUCTION

By self-organizing, the swarm systems consisting of large number of simple subsystems (nodes), have the potential of greater intelligence than the corresponding individual capabilities [1]–[3]. Such a concept is utilized in several biological phenomena, where individual entities from groups to improve their efficiency or to save energy. For example, an ant colony is able to find food in the shortest path; a fish school improves its ability to avoid predators; a bird flock renders it easier to migrate. The application of swarm systems can be seen in lots of fields including aerospace [4], agriculture [5], medicine [6] and communication [7].

Although the concept of swarm system has several potential advantages, its large-scale and distributed communication network make faults more likely and threaten the system security [8]. To ensure the safe and effective operation of the system, it is necessary to develop monitoring mechanisms for the overall system [9], [10]. As a tool for information acquisition, it is critical to install enough sensors to the design of the monitoring mechanisms. However, as the scale of the system increases, the number of sensors needs to be kept to a minimum to avoid excessive cost. Moreover, the complex network interactions require deliberative consideration of the

placement of the limited number of sensors so that the information acquisition capability is sufficient to complete the monitoring objectives. Therefore, for a swarm system, selecting appropriate sensors locations is a key issue to balance the cost and monitoring capability [11], [12].

As a measure of the monitoring capability, the concept of observability refers to the property of the system to recover the internal states through the external outputs [13]. To date, various observability criteria can be found for different kinds of systems [13]–[15]. Most existing results on observability of networked systems are derived under the assumption that the dimension of the state of each node is scalar [16]–[19]. Along this direction, several sensor selection and location strategies have been developed [17], [20], [21].

There are few results developed for the observability of networked systems with higher-dimensional nodes. The observability is investigated for a special class of networked systems with meromorphic dynamic nodes in [22], while a general networked system is considered in [23], [24] with every subsystem subject to external outputs. Note that the above results treat the overall networked system as a classic linear/nonlinear system, resulting in increased complexity and verification difficulties as the scale of the system and the dimension of nodes increase. As a result, for the sensor selection problem of large-scale swarm system with high-dimensional nodes, the above results may not provide an effective solution. As will be demonstrated below, for the swarm system with high-dimensional nodes, the multiple influencing factors including node-dynamics, network topology, inner coupling form, as well as the number and the position of the sensors, make the analysis of the observability more complicated. Therefore, it is important to clarify the effects of complex influencing factors on the observability of swarm systems.

Inspired by the above issues, in this paper, we focus on studying the general observability conditions for large-scale swarm systems, based on which a sensor selection algorithm that solves the necessary number and position to install sensors is developed. The main contributions are twofold:

This paper was supported in part by funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under grant agreement No. 951424 (Water-Futures) and the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 739551 (KIOS CoE); in part by China Postdoctoral Science Foundation under grant agreement No. 2022M721607.

- Firstly, a necessary and sufficient observability condition is deduced, which establishes the relations between the overall observability and the node dynamics, network topology, coupling mode, sensor locations into a low-order algebraic equations solution problem. Compared with existing results [22]–[24], such a condition effectively reduces the complexity of observability verification for large-scale systems.
- Secondly, based on the above necessary and sufficient result, some necessary conditions related to the form of measured outputs are derived, which provides the ideas of pre-selecting the necessary sensors. Moreover, a sensor selection algorithm that employs the above theoretical results is developed, which is proved to possess polynomial complexity. This algorithm is further applied to sensor selection problem for a UAV swarm system and the result shows the effectiveness of the proposed scheme.

This paper is organized as follows. After introducing some necessary mathematical foundations, the sensor selection problem associated with the modeling swarm system is formulated in Section II. Section III gives several general observability conditions related to the large-scale swarm systems. An algorithm for selecting the sensors is developed in Section IV, the effectiveness of which is verified in Section V by using a UAV swarm system. Section VI ends the paper with some conclusion remarks.

II. PRELIMINARIES AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Preliminaries

Throughout the paper, \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{C} denote the sets of real and complex numbers, respectively. Symbols \mathbb{R}^n (\mathbb{C}^n) is the set of n -dimensional real (complex) vectors and $\mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ ($\mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$) is the set of $m \times n$ -dimensional real (complex) matrices. For a matrix A , denote $\sigma(A)$ as the set of eigenvalues of A . Denote \otimes as the Kronecker product.

For N nodes, denote the adjacency matrix by L_{Ad} , whose element $L_{Ad}(i, j) = 1$ if there exists an edge from j to i , otherwise $L_{Ad}(i, j) = 0$. Let $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ be a *digraph* with node set $\mathcal{V} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ and edge set $\mathcal{E} = \{(i, j) \mid L_{Ad}(i, j) \neq 0\}$. In a digraph, a *path* is a sequence of distinct nodes with neighbor nodes as an edge in \mathcal{E} . Denote the *neighbors* of node i by $\mathcal{N}(i) = \{j \mid (j, i) \in \mathcal{E}\}$. A *component* is a subgraph $\mathcal{G}_i \triangleq (\mathcal{V}_i, \mathcal{E}_i)$ with $\mathcal{V}_i \subset \mathcal{V}$ including all end-nodes of the edge subset $\mathcal{E}_i \in \mathcal{E}$. A *contraction* \mathcal{C}_i is a component in which there exists a subset of nodes $\mathcal{V}_i \subset \mathcal{V}$ such that $|\mathcal{N}(\mathcal{V}_i)| < |\mathcal{V}_i|$, where $|\cdot|$ denotes the number of the elements in the set (\cdot) . A *strongly connected component* (SCC) is a component $\mathcal{S}_i \triangleq (\mathcal{V}_i, \mathcal{E}_i)$ such that there always exists a path between two arbitrary nodes $i, j \in \mathcal{V}_i$. In all SCCs $\mathcal{S} = \{\mathcal{S}_1, \dots, \mathcal{S}_p\}$, if all nodes in \mathcal{S}_i have no edge to the nodes of other SCCs, then \mathcal{S}_i is called a leaf SCC.

B. Problem formulation

Consider a swarm system consisting of N nodes described by the following equations:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_i(t) = A_0 \mathbf{x}_i(t) + B_0 \mathbf{u}_i(t), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state vector of the i -th node, $\mathbf{u}_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is the control input of the i th node, A_0 and B_0 are the system and input matrices with appropriate dimensions, respectively. Take for example the problem of achieving consensus [25]; in this case the following controllers can be designed to implement autonomic behavior of the swarm.

$$\mathbf{u}_i = \sum_{j=1}^N \beta_{ij} H_0 (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j) \quad (2)$$

where $\beta_{ij} \neq 0$ if there exists an edge from node j to node i satisfying $\sum_{j=1}^N \beta_{ij} = \sum_{j=1}^N \beta_{kj}$ and H_0 is a feedback matrix.

Consider a safety monitoring mechanism, as shown in Fig. 1, designed for the system (1)-(2). The effectiveness of such a mechanism depends on selecting appropriate sensors. Therefore, this paper focuses on investigating the sensor selection conditions that enable observers to generate accurate state estimates. Specifically, by introducing the additional sensors, the i th node dynamics (1) with controller (2) and measured output $\mathbf{y}_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}}_i(t) &= A \mathbf{x}_i(t) + \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N \beta_{ij} H \mathbf{x}_j(t) \\ \mathbf{y}_i(t) &= \delta_i C \mathbf{x}_i(t) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $H \triangleq B_0 H_0$ denotes the inner coupling matrix, $A \triangleq A_0 + \sum_{j=1}^N \beta_{ij} H$ is the new system matrix, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ is the sensing matrix determined by the structure of the sensor. Suppose that C is a full row rank matrix since otherwise it will produce a redundant or zero output. The scalar δ_i is a binary number with $\delta_i = 1$ if there exists a sensor in node i , otherwise $\delta_i = 0$, for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, $N \geq 2$.

Fig. 1. The schematic diagram of safety monitoring mechanism for a swarm system.

Let $L \triangleq [\beta_{ij}] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ denote the network topology and $\Delta \triangleq \text{diag}(\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots, \delta_N)$ the sensor selection matrix. Let $\mathbf{x} \triangleq [\mathbf{x}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{Nn}$ and $\mathbf{y} \triangleq [\mathbf{y}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{y}_N^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{Nm}$ be the total state and external output vectors of the whole swarm system. Then, the system (3) can be rewritten into the following compact form

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) &= \Phi \mathbf{x}(t) \\ \mathbf{y}(t) &= \Theta \mathbf{x}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi &\triangleq I_N \otimes A + L \otimes H \\ \Theta &\triangleq \Delta \otimes C.\end{aligned}$$

For this compact system, borrowing the concept of observability in linear system yields the following definition.

Definition 1: The system (4) is said to be *observable* if at the total interval $\mathcal{T} \triangleq [t_0, t_f]$, the initial state $\mathbf{x}(t_0)$ can be uniquely determined by $\mathbf{y}(t)$ for all $t \in \mathcal{T}$. \square

Such a property inflects the performance that the states can be fully reflected by the outputs, which is a prerequisite for the design of the estimators. Based on the above definition, the sensor selection problem can be formulated as follows.

Problem 1: For the swarm system (3)-(4), determine matrix Δ with the minimal rank (Δ), if possible, to render the whole system observable. \square

To solve Problem 1, the focus of this paper is on

- finding the conditions related to how the network topology L , the node-dynamics (A, C) , the sensor location Δ , and the inner interactions H affect the observability of the swarm system (3)-(4).
- developing a complexity acceptable algorithm ensuring the observability of the whole system, which gives the answer to how many sensors are installed and where.

III. OBSERVABILITY ANALYSIS FOR SWARM SYSTEMS

A. Main results

In this subsection, by combining the characteristics of the swarm system with the existing linear system theory, several necessary and/or sufficient observability conditions are proved.

Firstly, a general necessary and sufficient analytic condition is given.

Theorem 1: The swarm system (4) is observable if and only if, for any complex number s , the only matrix solution $\xi \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times N}$ of the following equations

$$\begin{cases} (sI - A)\xi - H\xi L^\top = 0 \\ C\xi\Delta = 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

is $\xi = 0$. \square

Proof: According to the PBH rank condition [26], the swarm system (4) is observable if and only if

$$\text{rank} \begin{bmatrix} sI_{N \cdot n} - \Phi \\ \Theta \end{bmatrix} = N \cdot n \quad (6)$$

for any complex $s \in \mathbb{C}$, which is equivalent to

$$\text{rank} \begin{bmatrix} sI_{N \cdot n} - \Phi & I_{N \cdot n} \\ \Theta & 0 \\ 0 & I_{N \cdot n} \end{bmatrix} = N \cdot (n + n). \quad (7)$$

Define matrix R as

$$\begin{aligned} R &\triangleq \begin{bmatrix} sI_{N \cdot n} - \Phi & I_{N \cdot n} \\ \Theta & 0 \\ 0 & I_{N \cdot n} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ L \otimes H & I \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} I_N \otimes (sI - A) & I_{N \cdot n} \\ \Delta \otimes C & 0 \\ L \otimes H & I_{N \cdot n} \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Since matrix $\begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ L \otimes H & I \end{bmatrix}$ is full rank, the condition in Eq. (7) is satisfied if and only if matrix R is of full column rank. Define $\zeta = [\zeta_1^\top, \zeta_2^\top, \dots, \zeta_N^\top]^\top$ with $\zeta_i \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times 1}$ and $\eta = [\eta_1^\top, \eta_2^\top, \dots, \eta_N^\top]^\top$ with $\eta_i \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times 1}$. Then one can obtain that R is of full column rank if and only if the solution of the following equations

$$\begin{aligned} (I_N \otimes (sI - A))\zeta + \eta &= 0 \\ (\Delta \otimes C)\zeta &= 0 \\ (L \otimes H)\zeta + \eta &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

is $\zeta = 0$ and $\eta = 0$. Define $\xi = [\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_N] \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times N}$. As a result, simplifying the above equations yields that condition Eq. (6) is satisfied if and only if the solution of both $(sI - A)\xi - H\xi L^\top = 0$ and $C\xi\Delta = 0$ is $\xi = 0$. This completes the proof. \blacksquare

It can be seen from Theorem 1 that to achieve observability of the whole system, all factors including the node-dynamics, network topology, coupling form as well as the sensor placement play important roles. Although the interaction of these factors is complicated, the sufficient and necessary relations that make the system observable can be verified by solving Equations (5). The most important point is that the above conditions effectively reduce the dimension of higher-order networked systems, making it possible to verify the observability of large-scale swarm systems analytically once all those factors are known.

Noticeably, with no knowledge about Δ , Theorem 1 is cumbersome to use, which leaves the Equations (5) with too many unknowns. Therefore, in what follows, by extending Theorem 1, we give some conditions that are used for constructing Δ , which is required at the beginning of sensor selection.

Theorem 2: Considering the swarm system (4), for some $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, if the network topology L is such that $\sum_{j=1}^N \beta_{ji} = 0$, then for the system to be observable it is necessary that $\delta_i = 1$ and (A, C) is observable. \square

Proof: Firstly, we prove that under the precondition, $\delta_i = 1$ is necessary. When selecting the complex number $s_0 \in \sigma(A)$ and $\xi_i \neq 0$ the eigenvector of A , the equality $(s_0 I - A)\xi_i = 0$ is satisfied by definition. Moreover, no matter what H is, when $\sum_{j=1}^N \beta_{ji} = 0$, the i th row of $H\xi L^\top$ is always a zero vector. Thus, even though every column of ξ except ξ_i must be zero, $(s_0 I - A)\xi - H\xi L^\top = 0$ is satisfied with a nonzero matrix solution. Then, it is easily shown that the above ξ with a nonzero column ξ_i is also a matrix solution of $C\xi\Delta$ if $\delta_i = 0$, no matter what C is. As a result, one can see that when $\sum_{j=1}^N \beta_{ji} = 0$ and $\delta_i = 0$, the conditions in Theorem 1 fail to hold, which implies the swarm system is unobservable in the case.

Secondly, we show that under the precondition, an observable pair (A, C) is necessary. According to the PBH eigenvector condition, if (A, C) is not a observable pair, then there exists a complex number $s_0 \in \sigma(A)$ with respect to the eigenvector ξ_i such that $C\xi_i = 0$. Therefore, repeating the above proof process yields that the conditions in Theorem 1

are not satisfied when $\sum_{j=1}^N \beta_{ji} = 0$ and (A, C) is an unobservable pair. This completes the proof. ■

From the above theorem, one can see that, in a swarm system, installing sensors for those leaf nodes is necessary. This can be explained by the fact that no other node can get information from the leaf nodes, which limits the possibility of sensors on other nodes to observe them. Also, to be observable, the observable node-dynamics is a precondition for those systems which have leaf nodes.

Theorem 3: Considering the swarm system (4) with a row full rank sensing matrix C , if (A, C_oH) is unobservable with $C_o \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} C \\ C_{(n-m) \times n}^e \end{bmatrix}$, where $C_{(n-m) \times n}^e \in \mathbb{R}^{(n-m) \times n}$ is a matrix such that $\det(C_o) \neq 0$, then for the system to be observable, it is necessary that every node $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ is with $\delta_i = 1$. □

Proof: If the pair (A, C_oH) is unobservable, there always exists a $s_0 \in \sigma(A)$ with respect to ξ_i such that $(s_0I - A)\xi_i = 0$ and $C_oH\xi_i = 0$. As a result, left multiplying C_o to the first equation of the conditions in Theorem 1 yields that $C_o(s_0I - A)\xi - C_oH\xi L^\top = 0$. Because square matrix C_o is full rank and thus invertible, the above equations imply that $(s_0I - A)\xi - H\xi L^\top = 0$ has a nonzero matrix solution ξ . For the node i with $\delta_i = 0$, as shown in Proof of Theorem 2, matrix ξ with the nonzero eigenvector ξ_i is also the solution of $C\xi\Delta = 0$. According to Theorem 1, in the case the overall system is unobservable. The proof is completed. ■

Theorem 3 provides a special case when all nodes are required to install sensors for observability. On the contrary, if there exists some node without a sensor, then the pair (A, C_oH) related to node-dynamics (A, C) and coupling form H should satisfy the observability condition.

Theorem 4: For the swarm system (4) to be observable, it is necessary that (L, Δ) is observable. □

Proof: If (L, Δ) is unobservable, there must exists a complex number $s_1 \in \mathbb{C}$ with respect to nonzero $\zeta \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ such that $(s_1I - L)\zeta = 0$ and $\Delta\zeta = 0$. Therefore, we have

$$(\zeta \otimes I_m) \mathbf{y}(t) = (\zeta \otimes I_m) \Theta \mathbf{x}(t), \quad (9)$$

which yields that

$$\begin{aligned} (\zeta^\top \otimes I_m) \dot{\mathbf{y}}(t) &= (\zeta \otimes I_m) (\Delta \otimes C) \dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) \\ &= (\zeta^\top \Delta \otimes C) (I_N \otimes A + L \otimes H) \mathbf{x}(t) \\ &= (\zeta^\top \Delta \otimes CA + \zeta^\top \Delta L \otimes CH) \mathbf{x}(t) \\ &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The above equation implies $\sum_{i=1}^N \zeta_i \dot{\mathbf{y}}_i(t) = 0$ no matter what $\mathbf{x}(t)$ is. Moreover, considering $\mathbf{x}(t_0) = 0$, we have $\mathbf{y}(t) = 0$ for all $t > t_0$. Consequently, the initial state $\mathbf{x}(t_0)$ can not be induced by $\mathbf{y}(t)$ and thus in the case the swarm system is unobservable according to Definition 1. This completes the proof. ■

The above theorem gives a result under which network topology and sensor selection, the swarm system may be observable. In fact, this result shows that the observability of the macro network is a necessary condition to ensure

the observability of the overall system. As a result, the existing sensor selection strategies for networks with one-dimensional nodes, for instance in [28], can be employed as the preliminary selection steps here.

B. Illustrated examples

In this subsection, we give two counter-intuitive examples, which shows the complexity of the observability held by the swarm systems and the effectiveness of theoretical results in Subsection III-A.

As shown in [17], a network L is structurally observable if and only if all unmatched nodes are equipped with sensors. For the swarm systems with high-dimensional nodes, however, the observability is more complicated as shown in the following examples.

Example 1: Consider a swarm system consisting of two nodes, with $\beta_{21} = 1$ and $\delta_2 = 1$. Suppose that each node has the following two-dimensional dynamics

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ 5 & 4 \end{bmatrix}, H = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ -4 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, C = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Each node is structurally observable since the only unmatched node 2 is equipped with a sensor. Also, it can be easily verified that (A, C) and (A, C_oH) are both observable. However, the overall swarm system is unobservable since $\text{rank}(\Theta, \Theta\Phi, \dots, \Theta\Phi^3) = 2 < 4$. This can be also verified by using Theorem 1: Substituting A, H, C, L, Δ into Eqs. (5) yields that when $s = 0$ there exist nonzero matrix solutions $\xi = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$ and $\xi = \begin{bmatrix} 6 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, which implies that the overall swarm system is unobservable. □

The above example illustrates that even though all the individual nodes have good observability properties, the overall observability may not be satisfied. On the other hand, the following example shows that although the individual nodes are not observable, the overall swarm system may be observable.

Example 2: Consider a swarm system consisting of two nodes with $\beta_{12} = \beta_{21} = 1, \delta_1 = 0, \delta_2 = 1$ and

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, C = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, H = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

It can be seen that although both (A, C) and (A, C_oH) are unobservable, the overall swarm system is observable. This can also be verified by using Theorem 1 since for arbitrary $s \in \mathbb{C}$ there exists only a zero matrix solution of Eqs. (5). □

IV. SENSOR LOCATION SELECTION

Given the node-dynamic (A, C) , network topology L and coupling mode H , for a swarm system, this section develops an algorithm to solve problem 1 based on the observability results obtained in Section III.

Firstly, according to Theorem 1, we have that once all factors A, C, L, H, Δ are known, whether Equations (5) have a unique solution and what the solution is can be verified, since in this case there exist $Nn + 1$ unknown variables including s and $\xi_{ij}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n, j = 1, 2, \dots, N$, in

$N(m+n)$ algebraic equations. Therefore, by using the mathematical simulation software, the necessary and sufficient observability condition in Theorem 1 can be verified. Here, we develop a solver called **Equations Solver** in MATLAB to solve Equations (5) that returns flag $f_s = 0$ for unobservability or $f_s = 1$ for observability, respectively. The source code of the above solver as well as all algorithms hereafter can be found at <https://github.com/qingkaiofkios/observability-of-swarm-systems>.

It should be stressed that compared with classic observability verification methods, e.g., observability Grammian [21], especially with the scale of the system increasing, the above observability criterion based on coupled equation solver reduces the difficulty of solving the problem. Specifically, only $Nn + 1$ unknowns are required to solve with at most $N(m+n)$ algebraic equations here while at least $Nn - 1$ iterations for Nn -dimensional matrix multiplication product are needed in classic methods. Based on the above solver, once a sensor selection candidate Δ is preliminarily given, whether it makes the overall system observability will be determined.

Secondly, we concentrate on selecting the sensors to satisfy the necessary conditions in Theorems 2-4. Note that as shown in Theorem 2, the swarm system may never be observable by adding sensors. Therefore, the sensor selectable property should be testified in advance. Considering the simplified characteristics of node-dynamics, the observability of (A, C) can be verified by using the observability rank test procedure, which returns the rank of the observability Grammian $G_O(A, C) \triangleq [C, CA, \dots, CA^{n-1}]$. Once the swarm system (4) is sensor selectable, an algorithm called **Netselect** [28] based on the following lemma is employed to guarantee the structural observability, which is proved to be necessary in Theorem 4.

Lemma 1 ([15]): A dynamical system is structurally observable if and only if in its system digraph $\mathcal{G}(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ the following conditions hold.

- 1) Every state node \mathcal{V}_i is the state node of a path that ends at an output.
- 2) There is a disjoint family of cycles and output-connected paths covering all state nodes in \mathcal{V} . \square

Moreover, the following corollary is given to state that once a swarm system (4) is sensor selectable, the structural observability is also sufficient to render the whole system observable.

Corollary 1: For a swarm system, if $\Delta = I_N$ is an observable sensor selection scheme but not the minimal, then the minimal structurally observable sensor selection schemes are also the solutions of Problem 1. \square

Proof: For a sensor selectable swarm system, it is sufficient to be observable for the system that the whole digraph $\mathcal{G}_w(\mathcal{V}_w, \mathcal{E}_w)$ with $\mathcal{V}_w = \{\mathbf{x}_{11}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{Nn}, \mathbf{y}_{11}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{Nm}\}$ satisfies Lemma 1. We firstly prove that in this case the structural observability of the network (L, Δ) makes condition 1 in Lemma 1 satisfied for \mathcal{G}_w . Suppose that in the case there exists a state $\mathbf{x}_{ij}, i \in \{1, \dots, N\}, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, not path-connected with any output in \mathbf{y} . For the hierarchical SCCs

of digraph \mathcal{G} of network L , if i belongs to a leaf SCC with more than two nodes, one can obtain that there exists no path determined by H directly or indirectly connecting \mathbf{x}_{ij} to the state \mathbf{x}_{pq} that directly connecting with \mathbf{y}_p . In fact, the above conclusion also holds if i does not belong to a leaf SCC and in this case every node $p = 1, 2, \dots, N$ without a sensor has the state $\mathbf{x}_{pq}, q = 1, 2, \dots, n$ not connecting with output. Therefore, once the system is sensor selectable, to make subsystem i observable, it is necessary (A, C) observable and $\delta_i = 1$. This requires $\Delta = I_N$, which contracts the assumed condition.

Secondly, we prove that in this case condition 2 in Lemma 1 is satisfied. It is well known that condition 2 is equivalent to the generic rank condition, i.e., condition 2 is satisfied if and only if

$$S - \text{rank} \begin{bmatrix} \Phi_s \\ \Theta_s \end{bmatrix} = Nn, \quad (11)$$

where $(\cdot)_s$ denotes a structural matrix that nonzero elements of (\cdot) can be arbitrarily assigned a value, and $S - \text{rank}(\cdot)$ denotes the maximum rank for all possible $(\cdot)_s$. This can be specifically seen as follows

$$S - \text{rank} \begin{bmatrix} A & \beta_{12}H & \cdots & \beta_{1N}H \\ \beta_{21}H & A & \cdots & \beta_{2N}H \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \beta_{N1}H & \beta_{N2}H & \cdots & A \\ \delta_1C & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \delta_2C & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & \delta_N C \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

From the above equation, we have that if Problem 1 has a non- $\Delta = I_n$ solution, then $S - \text{rank}[A^\top H^\top]^\top = n$. For observable (L, Δ) , since $S - \text{rank}[L^\top \Delta^\top]^\top = N$ and columns $[L_i^\top \Delta_i^\top]^\top, i = 1, \dots, N$ must be linear independent, Equation (12) is satisfied in this case.

In brief, in the case conditions in Lemma 1 are satisfied once (L, Δ) is structurally observable. This completes the proof. \blacksquare

As a result, a holistic sensor-selectable algorithm is integrated in Algorithm 1.

Note that in Algorithm 2, the outer-loop judgment statement takes Theorem 2 into account. This can be achieved by a low-dimensional rank Grammian procedure. Once the above step cannot give the answer whether the sensor is possible to select, the inner-loop judgement further considers the special case that $\Delta = I_N$ which includes conditions of Theorem 3. This is because that according to Eq. (6), in the proof of Theorem 1, the system (4) is more possibly to be observable with larger rank of Δ .

Algorithm complexity analysis: Firstly, to verify the sensor selectable property, Equations (5) is solved by using Gaussian elimination method, which possesses a polynomial complexity $\mathcal{O}((N(m+n))^3)$. Once the system is sensor-selectable, in Algorithm 3, to find the dilation sets, it requires $\mathcal{O}(N^{2.5})$ by using the so called Hungarian maximum matching algorithm

Algorithm 1: Once the sensor selectable property is verified by using Algorithm **SelTest**, the minimal sensor selection Algorithm **Netselect** is employed to satisfy the structural observability. Flag f_a denotes the completion of sensor selection, $-1, 0, 1$ representing "un-selectable", "pending" and "completed", respectively.

Input: Matrices A, C, H, L .

Output: Sensor distribution matrix Δ , if it is sensor selectable.

Initialization: set $f_a = 0$.

SelTest(A, C, H, L);

if The system is sensor-selectable **then**

 | Netselect(L);

else

 | $f_a = -1$, **END**;

end

Return f_a, Δ .

Algorithm 2: This Algorithm has been called in Algorithm 1 as **SelTest**, which returns the binary flag f_s .

Input: Matrices A, C, H, L .

Output: Sensor selectable flag f_s .

if column $L_i = 0$ for some $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ and

 rank $G_O(A, C) < n$ **then**

 | $f_s = 0$. **END**

else

 Set $\Delta = I_N$ and run **Equations solver** if Eqs. (5) are with only zero solution **then**

 | $f_s = 1$. **END**

else

 | $f_s = 0$. **END**

end

end

Return f_s .

[27]. Also, to find **leaf SCCs** the complexity is $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ as shown in [28]. As a result, the overall complexity of Algorithm 1 is $\mathcal{O}((N(m+n))^3)$. This polynomial complexity is acceptable for the large-scale swarm system since sensor selection is usually an off-line process that is achieved during the system design period.

Remark 1: It is worth noting that the implementation of the above algorithm is based on obtaining the global structure information of the system. Although this is a centralized strategy, it is reasonable to assume that the information of the system is known in advance since the implementation of the selection strategy is accomplished in the design stage of the monitoring mechanism. A promising extension of the above algorithm is for swarm systems with switching topologies during the running process. To achieve this, possible switching topologies can be incorporated into the sensor selection process. The largest union of sensors can then be chosen to ensure the successful implementation of the monitoring

Algorithm 3: This Algorithm has been called in Algorithm 1 as **NetSelect**, which simply summarizes and rewrites the graph based structural controllability algorithm in [28].

Input: Matrix L .

Output: Matrix Δ .

Construct network graph \mathcal{G} according to L ;

Find contractions $C_i, i = 1, \dots, l$;

Find SCCs \mathcal{S}_i and leaf SCCs \mathcal{S}_i^f ;

Add $N_{min} = |\mathcal{S}^l| + |\mathcal{C}| - \min |\mathcal{C} \cap \mathcal{S}^l|$ sensors for each contraction and each leaf SCC;

Return $m \geq 1$ group sensor selection schemes

$\Delta_i, i = 1, \dots, m$.

mechanism under different switching topologies. \square

V. SIMULATIONS EXAMPLE

We consider a distributed N -UAV swarm system, in which each autonomous vehicle can be modeled by the following linear model

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}}_p^i &= \mathbf{x}_a^i \\ \dot{\mathbf{x}}_a^i &= A_{damp} \mathbf{x}_p^i + \sum_{j=1}^N \beta_{ij} H_{coup} \mathbf{x}_a^j, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_p^i = [e_x^i \ e_y^i \ e_h^i]^\top$ denotes the position error in space along directions X -coordinate e_x^i , Y -coordinate e_y^i and height e_h^i ; $\mathbf{x}_a^i = [v_x^i \ v_y^i \ v_h^i]$ is the velocity along the above three directions. A_{damp} is a damping matrix used for increasing the velocities when the position error is large, otherwise decreasing the velocities. The velocity of vehicle i is also influenced by the velocity of its neighbor vehicles, which is formulated by coupling matrix H_{coup} here. $\beta_{ij} = 1/|\mathcal{N}(i)|$.

To estimate/observe the states of swarm system (13), a velocity sensor can be installed in a vehicle. To reduce the cost, we consider a sensor that can only measure the blended velocity signal, that is, sensor \mathbf{y}_i is a one-dimensional value linearly combined with the three-dimensional state corresponding to v_x^i, v_y^i and v_h^i , respectively.

As a result, the node dynamics are:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_3 & I_3 \\ A_{damp} & \mathbf{0}_3 \end{bmatrix}, C = [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0.2 \ 0.3 \ 0.2].$$

Suppose that $N = 25$ and the network topology is randomly generated, and shown as in Fig. 2. The system parameters are

$$A_{damp} = \begin{bmatrix} -10 & 0.2 & 0.2 \\ 0.2 & -10 & 0.2 \\ 0.2 & 0.2 & -10 \end{bmatrix}, H_{coup} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 & 0.2 & 0.2 \\ 0.2 & 0.5 & 0.2 \\ 0.2 & 0.2 & 0.5 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Applying Algorithm 1 to the above system (13) yields that the overall system is observable if the sensor set is selected as $S_\Delta = \{1, 3, 23\}$. To verify the effectiveness, we then check the rank of observability Grammian. As shown in Fig. 3, the rank increases to 150 if we add sensors to all nodes in S_Δ , which is consistent with our theoretical results.

Fig. 2. Network topology of the UAV swarm system (13)

Fig. 3. The observability Gramian rank change during the sensor selection process

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper provides some useful observability conditions for large-scale swarm systems, and presents a sensor selection algorithm that can be achieved in polynomial time. For future work, one interesting direction is to extend the proposed observability results into swarm system with nonlinear dynamics. Another promising direction is to extend the results of this paper to swarm systems with heterogeneous individuals. Moreover, some possible applications of the sensor selection algorithm, such as smart power grid and water distribution systems, require further investigation.

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